

PREFERENTIALLY ETCHED EPITAXIAL LIFTOFF OF INDIUM PHOSPHIDE

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ABSTRACT

The removal of an Indium Phosphide (InP) epitaxial layer from an InP substrate has been demonstrated by a preferentially etched epitaxial liftoff (PEEL) technique. The release layer is lattice matched InGaAs which is selectively etched. Results of several combinations of etchants are included. Two etchants yielded the desired peeling effect: HF: H₂O₂: H₂O (1:1:10) and citric acid:water:peroxide (1:1:8). Apiezon black wax is used to provide compression to the InP film to facilitate peeling of the film. The film and substrate remain in good condition after the PEEL process. Application of this technique to thin InP solar cells is discussed.

INTRODUCTION

The removal of epitaxial films from host substrates and the subsequent deposition on a new material has a wide variety of exciting applications. Besides the economic advantage of reusable substrates, the production of ultra-thin device layers has potential application in optoelectronic devices such as optical modulators or detectors, and thin film solar cells. Preferentially Etched Epitaxial Liftoff (PEEL) requires a release layer that is extremely selective with respect to the required etchant [1]. The sacrificial release layer which has been used thus far for PEEL is AlAs, with HF as the etchant and Apiezon W (black wax) used to provide the tension required for undercutting. Recent applications have been limited to GaAs thin film devices [2,3]. To date there have not been any significant applications of this technique to InP devices, principally due to the significant lattice mismatch between AlAs and InP, which does not exist between AlAs and GaAs. This requires a pseudomorphic deposition of AlAs to avoid lattice strains and dislocations in the InP epitaxial films. Stringent control of the Metal Organic Chemical Vapor Deposition (MOCVD) is required to fabricate the pseudomorphic PEEL structure.

EXPERIMENTAL

Indium gallium arsenide (InGaAs) is a ternary material whose lattice constant can be varied by changing the In/Ga ratio. At a ratio of 0.53/0.47 the lattice constant is matched to InP, thus the InGaAs layer may be as thick as desired without introducing any deleterious defects into the overlying InP epilayers. Candidates for selective etchants have been examined and will be described below.

The first attempt to produce a PEEL film utilized the known selectivity of the Caros etchant (H₂SO₄:H₂O₂:H₂O) in the ratio of 1:1:10 [4]. At room temperature this etchant was found to have insufficient selectivity to accomplish peeling without removing the InP thin film. The remaining substrate was polished and reusable. Work is continuing with this etchant at different temperatures.

The next attempt involved the Caros etchant in the ratio of 3:1:1. This etchant left the substrate with a black precipitate over much of the perimeter surface (see Fig. 1). The central area which was last to peel remained uncontaminated but was anisotropically etched (see Fig. 2).

Fig. 1. Perimeter substrate surface after peeling with Caros etchant (3:1:1) at room temperature.

Fig. 2. Central substrate surface after peeling with Caros Etchant (3:1:1) at room temperature.

The PEEL structures require a highly selective etchant. One such etchant for the structure shown in Figure 3 is HF: H₂O₂: H₂O (1:1:10) [5]. This etchant has been used successfully to produce PEEL InP films. Under room temperature conditions this etchant slowly removes the InGaAs layer without etching the InP.

Figure 3. InP PEEL Structure (Not to Scale)

Apiezon black wax provides compression to the InP film which causes the film to lift as it is undercut, permitting complete etching of the thin InGaAs layer. A mixture of trichloroethylene (TCE) and Apiezon type W wax (ratio 40 ml of TCE to 10 g of wax) was produced. The mixture is sprayed using the Spray Tool (air brush), creating a thin (~40 mil) layer of wax. It is then cured for 30 min. at room temperature and then cured 30 min. at 160°C. This curing process generates the compressive forces necessary for the peeling process. The edges are cleaned after curing with TCE and cotton swabs exposing ~.1 mm. of the epilayer edge.

The etchant time required was eleven days. The substrate was examined and is reusable with minimum polishing. The PEEL film exhibited some damage due to the long exposure to the etchant. Work is continuing to modify the etchant and/or process to reduce peeling time.

Once separated, the resulting free floating thin InP film, although supported by the Apiezon wax, is fragile and must be handled carefully. After diluting the etchant solution with deionized water, filter paper is placed underneath the film and the film is gently removed. Utilization of the filter paper permits the film to dry. After drying, the film can be placed on the desired substrate, or, if Van der Waals bonding is utilized for placement on a substrate, the film is transferred while still wet and then permitted to slowly dry. The wax is removed by sequential baths of TCE.

Several organic based etchants have proven to possess the required selectivity to be used for PEEL film development. Some of these etchants may allow the use of alternate processing sequences which would eliminate the fragile, free-floating, film stage. The structure shown in figure 3 could be bonded to a cover glass superstrate, tensioned to provide the required lifting force, and peeled.

One such etchant combination, Citric acid:H₂O₂:H₂O (1:1:8) [6], has been used to successfully peel the structure illustrated in Figure 3. Preliminary etching was done on samples of InP and InGaAs to determine the etch rate of each and hence the selectivity. A small part of an InP wafer was covered with Apiezon wax and was then placed in the etchant, at room temperature (23.5°C) for 30 minutes. After removing the wax, the sample was inspected with a Dektak Profilometer. No etching was detected. The same process was applied to a sample of GaInAs and an etch rate of .038 µm/min was measured. It should be pointed out that the etch rates, as determined by this planar method, are not valid under the constraint conditions imposed by the structure in Figure 3. However, the importance of the selectivity is crucial to a successful separation of the PEEL film. The etch time in the citric acid solution was 17 days, which is clearly excessive for commercial applications. Inspection of the PEEL film after removing the wax showed some damage due to the extended period of exposure to the etchant. Work is continuing to modify either the etchant and/or process to shorten the peeling time.

Also under development is the use of InP as the sacrificial release layer. This layer would be bounded on either side by GaInAs lattice matched layers to act as etch barrier layers (see Figure 4). Devices based on this inversion of the PEEL process include the InP/GaInAs monolithic cascade solar cell.

Figure 4. PEEL Structure with InP sacrificial layer (Edge View; Not to Scale)

An etchant combination of HCl:H₃PO₄ (3:1) [6] was used to attempt peeling. However, an excess of gas formation resulted in the irregular pattern shown on the substrate in Figure 5 and considerable damage to the film itself.

Fig. 5. Indium Phosphide substrate after etching with HCl:H₃PO₄

CONCLUSIONS

A variety of applications can be envisioned for a PEEL structure. One of which could be an PEEL InP top cell connected to a Si bottom cell to produce a highly efficient tandem solar cell structure. The PEEL technique would also permit easy fabrication of optoelectronic devices in which monolithic growth is often difficult. Current use of thin InP has been in optoelectronic integrated circuits (OEIC) and Si-LSiS. A laser diode (LD) on a Si substrate is a key device for developing viable III-V/Si OEICs.

REFERENCES

- [1] E. Yablonovitch, T. Gmitter, J. P. Harbison, and R. Bhat, *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, **51**, 26, 1987, pp. 2222-2224.
- [2] I. Pollentier, P. Emeester, P. Van Daele, TuG4 1991.
- [3] C. Van Hoof, W. De Raedt, M. Van Rossum, and G. Borghs, *Electronics Lett.*, **25**, 2, 1989.
- [4] G. A. Ferrante, J. P. Donnelly, and C. A. Armiento, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **130**, 5, 1983, pp. 1222-1224.
- [5] Institute of Physics Conference Series, *Gallium Arsenide and Related Compounds*, **91**, 1987, p. 717, 501.
- [6] T. P. E. Broekaert and C. G. Fonstad, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **139**, 8, 1992, pp. 2306-2309.